

**SATELLITE-DERIVED ESTIMATION OF RAINFALL
IN FORWARD-BACKWARD THUNDERSTORM PROPAGATION MODEL
USING NEURAL NETWORK EXPERT SYSTEM TECHNIQUES**

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ABSTRACT

This research presents an artificial neural network expert system technique for rainfall estimation from satellite data. Estimation results of rainfall from a forward-backward thunderstorm propagation model using neural network expert system techniques are given in this paper. Using artificial neural network expert system techniques, estimation or computation of rainfall amounts will be 10 times faster. The average error of rainfall estimates for the total precipitation event will be reduced to less than 30%, the currently achievable accuracy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Assessment of global climate change is a very important research area for the future of man and his environment. Rainfall estimation is one of key parameters in this research. During the past 20 years, there has been a great increase in our understanding of how satellite data can be used to estimate rainfall. But, even when we use interactive computer systems, the time needed to estimate rainfall is about a half hour. Verification results show that the average error for an event is about 30%.

To improve satellite based rainfall estimates, there are several areas that need to be addressed:

- (1) Currently only parts of pattern recognition techniques for rainfall estimation are used. New pattern recognition techniques based on the neural network architecture need to be developed.
- (2) Currently, it is very difficult to extract 3-dimensional information from a 2-dimensional image and to recognize plastic deforming subjects in real time. The Marr (1982) 2.5-D computational vision model is being used for estimating rainfall only. A new vision model based on the neural network for rainfall estimation is needed.

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- (3) There may not be enough rules, models and knowledge for rainfall estimation. New nonlinear rules and models for estimating rainfall are needed.
- (4) There are some expert systems for rainfall estimation, but most of them use decision tree techniques. These techniques have no parallel processing functions and have no nonlinear reasoning functions. Neural network expert system techniques having parallel processing and nonlinear reasoning functions for rainfall estimation are needed.

Neural network computing is an area that is receiving increased research interest. Since neural networks are massively parallel systems, neural network computers have tremendous speed and nonlinear advantages over traditional digital machines (Hang, 1987). Hopfield developed the first architecture of a neural network, the Hopfield network, (Hopfield, 1982). Carpenter (1989) had researched adaptive resonance theory (ART) architectures. A conventional neural network architecture is the Back Propagation (BP) neural network. Matsuoka (1989) introduced a new training model, the Integrated Neural Network (INN). INN can reduce training time for syllable signal processing. Linsker (1988) described a Self-Organized architecture in a perception network; this model can recognize special features of its environment, without being told which feature it should analyze.

Mertens and Kanet (1986) review the prospects for the implementation of an expert system in production and operations management. Methods for dynamically adapting the learning bias based on the characteristics of data are being developed by Gordon & Perlis (1989). Experience-based learning techniques are also being pursued to enable systems to exploit repetitive situations to improve their performance.

Several investigators, commencing their work in the late 1990s, showed that estimating rainfall from both geosynchronous and polar-orbiting satellite was feasible. A complete review of rainfall schemes that use visible, infrared, or microwave satellite data is presented by Barrett and Martin (1981). Most of the important facts about rain clouds have been extracted for use in the present estimation scheme. Currently, satellite-derived precipitation estimates (Scofield/Oliver, 1977) and 3-hour precipitation outlooks for convective systems, Extratropical cyclones, and tropical cyclones are computed on the NOAA/NESDIS Interactive Flash Flood Analyzer (IFFA) system and transmitted to National Weather Service Forecast Offices, and River Forecast Centers. However, this system permits the computation of rainfall estimates for only one convective system at a time. This is due to the considerable time needed for image processing, interpretation and the computation involved in the estimation of rainfall. If there are several storms occurring, an automatic estimation technique would be useful in providing rainfall estimates for the entire country. Digital satellite data is used in the estimation process. Neural network techniques are explored as a possible improvement to current techniques. This research applies artificial neural network expert system techniques to the enhancement of knowledge for automatic rainfall estimation from satellite data.

2. OUTLINE OF THE ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of a neural network expert system for satellite-derived estimation of rainfall can be seen in Fig. 1.

There are three parts of this architecture: (1) data pre-processing; (2) pattern recognition; (3) an expert system based on the neural network. All rule, mode, and knowledge provided by the expert will be saved in rule bases, model bases, and knowledge bases. Then rule reasoning, model reasoning, and knowledge reasoning neural networks will give the reasoning results. As the neural network is trained, the neural network expert system will output display information based on the display subsystem.

3. RESULTS OF ESTIMATION

The Scofield/Oliver (1977) Technique is using in NOAA for satellite-derived estimation of rainfall. The final formula of rainfall estimation is:

$$E = [(CT \text{ or } RB) + OS + M + SE] * MC * S$$

where: **CT** = cloud top temperature + cloud growth factor

RB = rain burst factor

OS = overshooting top factor

M = merger factor

SE = saturated environment factor

MC = moisture correction

S = speed of storm

E = half-hour convective rainfall estimate (inches)

In a study by Xie/Scofield (1989), where the Scofield/Oliver Technique was used, it was found that most flash floods were produced by backward propagating thunderstorm called Mesoscale Convective System (MCSs). Synoptic patterns were presented for forward and backward propagating MCSs. The results for satellite-derived estimation of rainfall from the forward-backward propagation model for eight cases are presented in Table 1. When the Scofield/Oliver Technique was used, the largest error of the rainfall estimates was 48%. The average error of the operator-computed IFFA rainfall estimates is 24.3%.

Reasoning networks of a neural network expert system were trained by using the HDS 9000 mainframe computer. A Back-Impedance Algorithm was used to train the artificial neural network. After all the information had been received, the satellite-derived estimation of rainfall only needed about 2 seconds of HDS 9000 CPU time to execute. The results of rainfall estimates using artificial neural network expert system techniques for the forward-backward propagation model are given in Table 1. The average error of rainfall estimation is about 1.45%.

For example, in case 3 of Table 1, the rainfall estimation error of Xie/Scofield's study is 23.7%, the satellite picture can be seen in Fig 2. If the neural network expert system technique was used, in case 3 of Table 1, the rainfall estimation error was only 0.5%.

The biggest error resulting from neural network expert system techniques is -3.9%, case 7, Table 1. The largest error of Xie/Scofield's study was 48%, which occurred in case 8 of Table 1.

4. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Artificial neural network expert system technique and the use of artificial neural network expert system for rainfall estimates are important tools to the enhancement of accuracy for automatic rainfall estimation from satellite data. The experimental results show:

- (1) Because the neural network expert system is a massive parallel processing system, it makes estimating rainfall 10 times faster. In this paper, after all information has been received, the satellite-derived estimation of rainfall needs about 2 seconds of HDS 9000 CPU time to execute.
- (2) Because the neural network expert system is a nonlinear reasoning system, it results in the average error of rainfall estimates for total precipitation event to be reduced to less than 30%, the currently achievable accuracy. In this work, the average error of rainfall estimates for the forward-backward thunderstorm propagation model for cases from May to August is about 1.45%.

This study only considered rainfall estimation using the forward-backward thunderstorm propagation model and the artificial neural network expert system technique for the period of May to August. This study will next consider the satellite signatures that compose the convective rainfall estimation algorithm using neural expert system techniques.

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6. REFERENCES

Because of limited space, all of the references are not cited

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Figure 1. The Outline of Architecture

Table 1 Results of Estimation

No.	Date	Location	X/S E Inch	X/S Error %	Observation Inch	NN E Inch	NN Error %
1	8/13 1985	WI	3.75	-31.8	5.5	5.45	-0.9
2	8/21 1984	KS	3.87	- 3.3	4.0	3.95	-1.3
3	7/03 1983	MN	4.75	23.7	3.84	3.86	+0.5
4	6/26 1985	NE	4.93	20.2	4.1	4.10	0.0
5	7/16 1984	TN	5.08	21.0	4.2	4.11	-2.1
6	7/04 1983	KS	7.44	24.0	6.0	5.84	-2.6
7	7/21 1987	ND	7.84	22.5	6.4	6.15	-3.9
8	5/03 1987	NW MO	10.36	48.0	7.0	6.98	-0.3
Average		Error	24.3%		Average	Error	1.45%

X/S: Xie/Scofield's Study; E: Estimation of Rainfall
 NN: Neural network expert system technique

Fig 2. Satellite picture in case 3 of table 1